

Supplementary material accompanying “A novel framework for studying oceanic freshwater transports, and its application in discerning the modelled fate of freshwater around the coast of Greenland”

Fraser William Goldsworth

^aMax Planck Institute for Meteorology, Bundesstraße 53, Hamburg, 20146, , Germany

1. Introduction

This supplementary material contains figures used in assessing the realism of the model’s atmospheric component.

In each of the figures, modelled fields are shown alongside fields from the ERA5 reanalysis product (Hersbach et al., 2023). ERA5 data is all averaged over the time period 1950 to 1960. Model data is averaged between model years 50 and 60.

Figures show 10 m winds (figures 1 & 2), precipitation (figure 3), and net heat flux into the ocean (figure 4).

Generally speaking, the ICON and ERA5 fields look very similar; however, it should be noted that ERA5 is a reanalysis rather than observational product. Differences in the fields may arise from biases in the IFS-model used to generate ERA5 or biases in the ICON model. Despite this limitation, I have made the decision to compare to ERA5 data as it is commonly used to drive the ICON-Ocean model (and many other models) in forced ocean simulations.

References

Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J.N., 2023. ERA5 monthly averaged data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS) doi:10.24381/cds.f17050d7. Accessed on 27-Jan-2025. [Dataset].

Figure 1: Average zonal wind speed at 10 m above the surface in the ICON model (left) and ERA5 reanalysis product (right), during winter (top) and summer (bottom).

Figure 2: Average meridional wind speed at 10 m above the surface in the ICON model (left) and ERA5 reanalysis product (right), during winter (top) and summer (bottom).

Figure 3: Average precipitation in the ICON model (left) and ERA5 reanalysis product (right), during winter (top) and summer (bottom).

Annual mean net heat flux

Figure 4: Annually averaged net heat fluxes at the surface in the ICON model (left) and ERA5 reanalysis product (right). Hatching shows regions where the annual average sea-ice concentration in the ICON model is above 10%. Differences in the hatched regions arise from different heat flux treatments over sea-ice: in ICON, heat fluxes from sea-ice to the atmosphere contribute to the net heat flux, whereas in ERA5 they do not. Positive heat fluxes are directed into the ocean.